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Teaching with Settlement in Mind

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ABSTRACT

This paper describes one way in which a community-based program for adult learners with limited L1 schooling facilitates the transformative heart of the REFLECT model (based on Freirean principles) within a settlement-focused context.

INTRODUCTION

Traditionally, second language (L2) and literacy programs developed for newcomers to Canada have been settlement focused. Language Instruction for Newcomers to Canada (LINC) teacher guides suggest content like “Finding a Home” and “Working in Canada” (TCDSB, 2012). LINC is the largest program accessed by adults developing print literacy skills for the first time while learning the target language. Smaller community-based programs also exist to address the needs of such learners. No set national or provincially mandated curriculum framework exists for these programs, which rely on their own sense of learner needs to shape program design. The community-based program described in this paper is, like LINC, settlement focused. However, it draws on a participatory approach to learning and teaching while drawing on a curriculum framework to guide facilitators' understanding of literacy development. The participatory origin of the program allows for learning opportunities that are responsive to learners' immediate needs and aims to hold to the transformative nature at the heart of participatory literacy education (Freire, 2007). This paper describes an example of settlement-focused transformative learning for adult newcomers with limited first language (L1) literacy.

Settlement can be defined as the dynamic process through which newcomers “achieve full equality and freedom of participation in society, and society [gains]

access to the full human resource potential in its immigrant communities” (Ontario Council of Agencies Serving Immigrants, 2000). While settlement counsellors work to address the immediate needs of newcomer communities, the continuous nature of LESLLA training programs means facilitators are in a unique position to address settlement concerns of LESLLA learners.

This paper looks into the value of ensuring that learners develop the skills to access settlement services and of instructors considering and removing barriers to those services as part of unit planning and classroom teaching. We describe the small program from which this discussion arose before looking into the REFLECT (Regenerated Freirean Literacy Through Empowering Techniques, Archer & Cottingham, 2009) approach on which the program is based. Next, we discuss models for instruction with a focus on settlement themes. The paper then describes an approach to unit planning used in the author’s classroom teaching. Factors considered in these integrated units are organized into 4 main areas of focus: frontloading, skills-building, identifying available resources, and creating opportunities for connections between LESLLA learners and service providers. We offer examples of ways this has been implemented in their context.

We believe that the 4th area, creating opportunities for connections, is what makes classroom teaching transformative in nature. The outline presented is not meant to be a one-size-fits-all curriculum framework, but rather a tool that may be useful in ensuring all of these aspects are included in unit planning in a L2 literacy programs.

Context and Rationale

In this section, we describe the community-based program in which settlement-focused instruction is implemented. A description of the REFLECT model on which this program is based is followed by a discussion of research on literacy instruction compared with literacy practices and a look at ways in which content-based instruction can be transformative in nature.

The Context. We work with an immigrant-serving agency in Canada. Both work mainly with LESLLA learners: as a facilitator in an ELL literacy program and as a learning support specialist with language training programs. The present language training program is community-based and historically participatory in nature. Target language and literacy skills are embedded in contexts that are relevant to learners’ lives.

In this program, it is not unusual for learners to bring concerns to the group and to program staff. Learners might bring a letter to their teacher for clarification or ask for help to fill out application forms for subsidized transit passes. Others talk to their teachers about concerns at home, like increases in monthly rent or family conflict. Learners initially referred to learning support services may ask questions about finding winter clothes or managing their prescription medication. Some of these concerns can be addressed by program staff. For instance, teachers can work with a learner to complete simple, low-stakes paperwork. Other questions are beyond the knowledge and expertise of program staff and are best addressed by a settlement counsellor, social worker

or family counsellor within the organization or in the community. In addition to helping learners themselves or referring individual learners to the appropriate supports, settlement issues can be addressed within program curriculum in such a way that learners develop skills and knowledge to navigate systems independently. This type of instruction embeds language and literacy skills development in settlement-themed contexts that are relevant to learners' everyday needs. We have not completed research to determine the how effective this approach to instructional design is. The classes in which this model is implemented, however, are generally filled to capacity and attendance rates are high.

Curriculum and Instruction. In its inception, program developers used the REFLECT or Regenerated Freirean Literacy Through Empowering Techniques (Archer & Cottingham, 2009) as a model for the present program. The REFLECT approach is designed to address immediate needs of literacy participants in rural communities in Bangladesh, El Salvador and Uganda. Adherents to the REFLECT approach use materials available in the community or create their own materials rather than use commercial texts or readers. In the present L2 literacy program, facilitators continue to rely on learners to inform class content, though program facilitators generally use a combination of teacher-made and commercially available texts alongside learner-generated texts. At the heart of the REFLECT approach and in keeping with Freirean methods is its aim to encourage learner dialogue about issues important to them and to empower learners to take action in their communities. Learners are viewed as adult decision-makers and classroom content begins from a position of respect for the learners' existing knowledge and skills (REFLECT Action, 2009). In an action research project looking into the efficacy of the (at the time) newly developed REFLECT approach, Archer and Cottingham (2009) found positive outcomes beyond the classroom: learners were more involved in local community organizations and worked to improve economic and environmental conditions. They note that literacy skills unto themselves do not create empowerment, but that the REFLECT approach is successful because of the way it balances literacy skills and principles aimed at empowerment.

Recent changes to federal policy mandate that LINC programs across the country follow a Portfolio Based Language Assessment (PBLA) model with the goal of standardizing LINC levels across the country. As a result of changes to the Canadian Language Benchmarks, benchmarks for ESL literacy learners now align to benchmarks for newcomers with prior formal education. The program described in this article, however, refers to the ESL Literacy Curriculum Framework (Bow Valley College, 2010) for several reasons. First, the ESL Literacy Curriculum Framework has articulated 18 reading and writing outcomes that are not context specific. The writing outcome "Fill Out Forms," for example, works in a health, transportation or jobs unit where paperwork is required for access to services or employment. This highly supportive document breaks outcomes down into small increments. This means that teachers are guided as they scaffold instruction for learners at various levels from Foundation to Phase III Adequate. Outcomes are not tied to specific themes and teachers in

the participatory program aim to provide programming that is responsive to the particular class of learners they are working with at the time. For instance, one group of learners described challenges they were experiencing in the workplace: one lost her job as a result of being unable to read her work schedule. Her teacher developed a unit on working with different types of schedules, which falls under the reading outcome of “Interpreting lists, tables, charts and graphs.” When another teacher learned that learners in her class were experiencing difficulty navigating the city, she developed a unit on transportation.

The L2 literacy program described above is community-based and settlement-focused. Grounded in the REFLECT approach to literacy learning and teaching, it also draws on generalized reading and writing outcomes to inform instruction. In this way, the program embeds language and literacy skills development within settlement content in a way that has the potential to improve learners’ lives outside of the classroom.

RESPONSIVE INSTRUCTION WITH LESLLA LEARNERS

In this section, we look into connections between L2 and literacy skills and learners’ expressed needs in existing literature. This is followed by a look at combining settlement-focused content-based instruction with a transformative approach to learning and teaching. Lastly, the value of including cultural capital in instructional planning is touched upon.

In her volume on *Cultural Practices of Literacy*, Purcell-Gates (2006) highlights the frequent disconnect between learners’ literacy practices and classroom literacy instruction. She notes we know so little about the literacy practices of various sociocultural groups that we are unable to begin tying learners’ actual literacy practices to design literacy curriculum and instruction in an informed way. There is, however, some beginning research on the types of skills learners wish to develop during their time in L2 language and literacy programs. In Gonzalves’ (2011) interviews of Yemeni women, the overarching reason for attending LESLLA classes was ‘we want to depend on us.’ In a small qualitative study on the interplay between L1 literacy and settlement (Wall, 2017; Wall, this volume), 5 LESLLA learners talked about the roles of L2 and literacy in their lives in Canada. Asked for their advice to teachers, they suggested including topics like parenting norms in Canada, reading signs, and asking for directions.

Given the participatory nature of the present program, there is flexibility in program content, so long as the generalized reading and writing outcomes are addressed. This ‘hybrid’ model, one that draws on learners’ life experiences and goals while following a set of outcomes creates an environment in which program content and target language and literacy skills are complementary. That said, there is an added step to be taken if learning is to be transformative in nature.

Like Canada, much of ELL literacy programming in Australia is settlement focused (Chapman & Williams, 2015). Chapman and Williams note that, when policy directs content, there is a risk of programs transmitting information to

learners rather than engaging learners in skills and content important to them in a way that will improve their circumstances beyond the classroom. Content-based instruction can, however, be transformative when it moves beyond the learning of content and what Kerns (2000) terms available designs (e.g. vocabulary, procedural knowledge and declarative knowledge) toward sociocultural content (Chapman & Williams, 2007; Kerns, 2000).

Bigelow's (2007) case study of social and cultural capital's role in a LESLLA high school learner's academic success presents a convincing argument for the role of schools in developing cultural capital. Cultural capital includes knowledge of how systems work and the skills to accomplish tasks within those systems (Bourdieu & Passeron, 1977, as cited in Bigelow, p.2). A recent study including LESLLA learners in Canada found cultural capital to be an important factor to participants' ability to access services (Wall, 2017). Participants shared stories of times when lack of information placed them in vulnerable situations. One described a time she was lost overnight after realizing she did not know how to indicate her stop bus stop and being taken to the final terminal. Another spoke about a harrowing experience with child welfare in which she nearly lost her children. Participants recommended that teachers provide information about cultural norms and connections to community resources in ELL literacy programs as part of their classroom instruction.

Chapman and Williams (2015) note,

Transformative learning is about engaging in practical ways in the environment and community that the students live in. In the building of partnerships, the teacher is an advocate in the community, a participant in the activities and a mentor to the learners. (p.46)

An Approach to Settlement-Focused Content and LESLLA Learning

Frontloading	Background knowledge Language and vocabulary
Related Skills	Skills required to access the service
Identifying Resources	Where and how to access services
Community Connections	Guest speakers Field trips

Figure 1: Outline for Teaching with Settlement in Mind

When working in a settlement-focused context, transformative learning involves improving the circumstances of learners lives outside the classroom (Chapman & Williams, 2015). One way to do this is by incorporating the development of cultural capital into LESLLA classrooms. In the sample unit plans that follow, we have attempted to tie language and literacy skills to the development of cultural capital with the aim of transformative learning and teaching. Section 3 outlines an approach to instructional planning where both

facets are considered. The approach described in this section includes frontloading, skills building, identifying available resources, and creating opportunities for connections between LESLLA learners and service providers.

Frontloading

Frontloading refers to the activation and teaching of background knowledge as well as the specific language and vocabulary that learners require for understanding the theme or topic being taught in the classroom. Frontloading leads to increased learner comprehension and focus (Adams, 2012; Murray Stowe, 2010). To complete the real-world task of finding items and prices in a second-hand store, learners need to have basic shopping vocabulary, understand the local currency, and the ability to read prices.

Building Related Skills

Building related skills is the scaffolding that facilitates learner success in the classroom. Specific skills include such things as addition and subtraction, filling in forms, reading maps, writing messages, following instructions and interpreting charts. These skills need to be pre-taught in order to ensure learner success. For example, to successfully complete the real-world task of finding items and prices in a second-hand store, learners need to have skills in basic numeracy, addition and subtraction, reading receipts and flyers and asking for assistance.¹

Identifying Resources

Introducing learners to community resources that they can access is essential to the integration process. Learners need to know what services are available in their communities. When facilitators share simplified information about agencies, supports and services in their communities, they support holistic integration for their learners. For example, in a unit on financial literacy, information can be shared about tax clinics, basic financial literacy courses and supports in accessing services.

Forming Connections with Service Providers and Community Resources

Connections can be forged with service providers and community resources through both field trips and classroom presentations. This type of exposure helps LESLLA learners feel comfortable accessing services and resources. Presentations from various agencies and community service providers with first language support will ensure that learners comprehend the information and are familiar with how to access services that support positive integration. Field trips have the added value of providing learners with an opportunity to travel to the agency or community resource and to access services for the first time with the guidance and support of a facilitator.

¹ See Vinogradov, 2009 and Vinogradov & Liden, 2009 for more on this and other activities for building L2 and literacy skills)

WHAT IT LOOKS LIKE: EXAMPLES FROM THE CLASSROOM

Teaching with settlement in mind may not look dramatically different from a well-organized L2 Literacy class that engages students in topics that are interesting and meaningful to them. However, when an instructor plans themes, topics and lessons within this suggested outline, he or she is explicitly seeking ways to address settlement concerns by providing the language, skills, knowledge and connections that learners need for successful settlement and integration into their communities. In addition, the instructor can provide support during, before or after class with brief, simple tasks that learners are struggling with such as making appointments with a counsellor or correctly filling in paperwork. The outline below provides an accessible, practical means of organizing our approach to ensure that we are incorporating the pressing settlement needs of L2 literacy learners into our teaching. We will look at examples within 3 different units: financial literacy, healthcare and community.

Financial Literacy Unit – Shopping for Clothes

Financial literacy is an incredibly complex and wide-ranging theme including the areas of banking, budgeting, and shopping. Regardless of which area of financial literacy the instruction will focus on, there is significant overlap in the background knowledge, vocabulary and skills required by learners, as shown in Figure 2.

Frontloading	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Basic numeracy, local currency, understanding prices and totals • Shopping vocabulary, banking vocabulary, how to ask for help
Related Skills	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Addition and subtraction • Reading receipts and bills • Using an ATM • Using a calculator • Reading flyers • Dialogue practice
Identifying Resources	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Connecting with a counselor for help in applying for or maintaining financial support • Volunteer tax clinics • Non-profit financial literacy organizations • Where to find interpretation support
Community Connections	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Budgeting presentation with first language support • Second-hand shopping field trip • Bank visit field trip • Grocery store field trip

Figure 2: Sample Unit Plan – Shopping for Clothes

Frontloading. In a unit on clothes shopping, the instructor can begin by talking about what learners are wearing to class that day and by looking at images from clothing store flyers in order to activate the learner's background knowledge. This can be the basis for a classroom discussion with questions such as:

- What are you wearing today?
- Are you wearing a sweater? A t-shirt? Socks?
- Where do you buy clothes in your community?
- Which store has the best prices?
- Where do you buy clothes for adults?
- Where do you buy clothes for children?

Even with very limited English language skills, learners are often able to talk at least in general terms about where they shop as it is a necessity of everyday life. This activity also serves as a needs assessment by providing the instructor with information about learners' experiences and present language skills.

The next step is vocabulary building which can be done through a variety of activities, beginning with oral vocabulary. Repeating the names of clothing items that learners are wearing each day is a fun and engaging activity for learners. The use of picture flashcards is another important tool in building oral vocabulary with activities such as the flyswatter game, bingo, categorization activities (winter vs. summer clothes), and oral partner practice. When learners are familiar with the oral vocabulary, they can be introduced to the written vocabulary through flashcards. Learners can match picture and word cards, play bingo with the word cards, and use the cards as a word bank to label images and complete writing activities. Phonics, reading and writing activities can also be incorporated into this stage of the teaching. It is also important to explicitly teach learners what kinds of clothing are required for their safety and the safety of their families during the winter season.

In addition to gaining basic competency with the clothing vocabulary, instruction can be incorporating numeracy into the classroom with activities such as counting learners and classroom items as well as games and activities to build number recognition. When learners have some basic numeracy knowledge, explicit instruction on reading money amounts and using the local currency can begin. Most learners are highly motivated to learn about money as it is essential to their survival and independence. Educational money for use in the classroom is a fun and accessible tool to teach about currency. Activities such as listening to the teacher and showing the amount requested, finding totals using educational money, and reading and writing dollar amounts all build basic numeracy skills and are essential to the process of frontloading.

Related Skills. When learners are familiar with clothing vocabulary and local currency, instruction can move on to the related skills learners need. The use of flyers in the classroom can help learners be familiar with reading money amounts in a real-life context. Practicing adding and subtracting different money amounts by physically manipulating educational money can help make this challenging task more accessible. Teaching learners how to use the calculator on

their phone is highly motivating and provides learners with a tool that supports their independence. In addition, learning to read receipts with the use of instructor-modified or real world receipts is an essential skill for successful integration. When learners have gained competency in the related skills, the instructor can set up a “store” in the classroom with images and prices of clothing around the room. Learners can ask for help, choose items to purchase, and pay with the educational money while other learners can play the role of cashier and sales help. This fun and engaging activity prepares the learners for the real-world experience of a field trip to a second-hand clothing store.

Identifying Resources. In regions that have dangerously cold winter weather, sharing information with learners about free or low-cost winter clothing programs is a practical way to support learners in meeting their basic needs, thereby increasing their readiness for learning. Using speaker mode during class time to phone a program like a clothing bank and find out key information for accessing the program models this skill for learners and serves as a listening exercise. Bringing in a speaker from a financial literacy organization to provide suggestions and ideas of ways to save money supports learner integration. Ideally, this type of presentation is done with first-language support through the use of volunteer interpreters or learners with more advanced listening and speaking skills. These types of presentations enable learners to become more familiar with the supports available to them in the community so they can make informed decisions about accessing assistance for their families. In addition, learning about which organizations provide income tax preparation clinics and how to access this service is integral to successful integration.

Community Connections. A practical way to conclude a unit on clothes shopping is with a field trip to a local second-hand store. There are a myriad of learning activities associated with this type of field trip, before, during and after the activity. Before the field trip, activities can include finding the best route to the location using digital transit and mapping apps, creating a class plan for the day, and making lists of clothing items that learners may hope to purchase for their families. Pictures taken en route to the store and during the field trip can be used later as a tool to prompt the writing of a class story. In the second-hand store, learners can find write the names of clothing items, find prices, and ask for help. When the formal learning activity is complete, learners can be given time to explore the store and even purchase needed items for family members.

Following the field trip, writing a class Language Experience story can lead to many group and individual reading and writing tasks with vocabulary and ideas that the learners are very familiar with. In addition to the formal learning opportunities associated with a field trip to a second-hand store, learners become more comfortable using transit to access an invaluable community resource and are familiar with a new shopping option for finding quality, low cost items for themselves and their families.

Health Unit – Going to the Doctor

As with financial literacy, healthcare is a very complex theme with many different areas of focus including human anatomy, health care systems, healthy

eating, and wellness. In all areas of a health-related theme, the learners will require similar background knowledge, vocabulary and skills in order to be successful in moving towards a healthy lifestyle, which is essential to individual and family integration as shown in Figure 3.

Frontloading	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How the healthcare system is organized: family doctors, walk-in clinics, urgent care centres, emergency departments, 9-1-1 • Body vocabulary, health vocabulary
Related Skills	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Filling out forms • Reading directions • Using a calendar • Calling 9-1-1
Identifying Resources	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Learning what service to access for different health concerns • How to ask for first language support • Finding help to book appointments
Community Connections	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Presentations on topics such as breast health, sexual health, healthy eating, etc. • Book interpreter support for presentations • Field trip to an urgent care centre

Figure 3: Sample Unit Plan – Going to the Doctor

Frontloading. While the ultimate goal of this unit is that learners will be feel comfortable accessing health care with some measure of independence, instruction needs to begin with the required background knowledge so that learners have the foundation on which to build their competence. Begin with talking about the body, having learners show various body parts called out by the instructor or by naming body parts on themselves. Playing a version of “Simon Says” allows the instructor to assess the learners’ vocabulary while learners are engaged in a fun, kinesthetic learning activity. Picture and word flashcards can be used to develop vocabulary with activities such as bingo, matching, labelling, and partner question and answer exercises.

When learners are familiar with body vocabulary, instruction can begin with health and sickness vocabulary such as headache, fever, and sore throat. Engaging in the same learning activities with the new vocabulary using picture and word flashcards reduces the cognitive load for learners. When learners are familiar with the activities, they can concentrate fully on building their competence with the new vocabulary. In addition, picture and word cards can be used as prompts as learners ask each other, “What is the matter?” Another fun and engaging activity for vocabulary building is to have either the instructor or learners act out various ailments while the class guesses what the health problem is.

Familiarity with the vocabulary of health problems leads to learning about where to access health care services. It is important for learners to know the vocabulary for unique health care access points in their community, including family doctors, walk-in clinics, urgent care centres, hospitals, community health centres and emergency medical care.

Related Skills. There are a myriad of skills related to accessing health care including filling in forms. The complexity of most authentic medical forms and questionnaires may preclude their use with LESLLA learners, but teacher-developed forms can introduce learners to the information needed as well as the types of questions that will be asked. Learning how to use identification to fill in personal information on forms will build learners' confidence in real-life scenarios. Spending 5 minutes daily to practice orally spelling first and last names as well as clearly stating one's address and phone number will develop learner competence. Whole class and partner practice of simple dialogue for a doctor's office will give learners a template for use in real-life scenarios. Setting up a doctor's office role play in the classroom allows learners to use all of the skills they have used in an authentic-type situation. Learners can check in with reception, state and spell their name, fill in the form given them and wait to be called into the doctor's office where they will state their health problem. This type of learning activity is highly motivating as learners recognize its value in their day to day lives.

Identifying Resources. Navigating health care systems is a complex task. Understanding where to access care for what type of problem is key to getting the needed help. For example, many newcomers will go to the hospital for any medical issue that arises, wasting hours waiting in the emergency room for a problem that could have easily been treated by a family doctor or at a walk-in clinic. Specific instruction on health care access points in your particular community is essential. Once learners are familiar with the health care options such as family doctors, walk-in clinics, help lines, emergency departments etc., the class can engage in activities where learners categorize health ailments under the appropriate place to find care for that particular problem. Instruction on how to ask for first language support in hospitals or clinics is also needed. Partner dialogue practice and role play in class will equip learners for their future health care needs. A presentation from an immigrant-serving agency will familiarize learners with help available to them if they need assistance to book appointments or to access interpreter support for medical visits. As a significant point of contact for LESLLA learners, the instructor is in a unique position of providing assistance with brief tasks such as confirming appointments, looking up transit routes to appointment locations and ensuring learners have essential identification and health care documentation needed for their appointments. While these tasks are outside of the realm of literacy and language instruction, spending a few minutes to assist learners with such chores can significantly reduce learner stress.

Community Connections. Presentations on specific health care issues faced by the population of your class can be a useful way to build connections to community services. A dietician can present on healthy eating and managing

diabetes, or a health facilitator can present on screening programs. If it is possible, a field trip to an urgent care centre can familiarize learners with the protocols they can expect, how to access interpretation services, and what documentation is required. This type of knowledge will enable learners to take responsibility for their own and their family's health care needs.

Community Unit - Accessing Community Services

Being able to navigate one's community and access its resources is essential to successful integration. Knowledge of how the community is organized, how to move around in the community and what types of services are available all contribute to the development of a healthy sense of belonging. By building on the key background knowledge, vocabulary and skills that learners require, teachers can create lessons that will promote learner integration as shown in Figure 4.

Frontloading	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Concepts of country, city, community, neighbourhood, address, and home ● Places in my community: bank, library, swimming pool, etc. ● Directions: turn right, go straight, across from, etc.
Related Skills	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Reading maps ● Giving and following directions ● Reading signs ● Filling out forms ● Reading a bus schedule ● Asking for help
Identifying Resources	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Libraries ● Recreation centres ● Immigrant services agencies ● Emergency services
Community Connections	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Presentations from an immigrant serving agency ● Presentations from city services, such as police and fire departments ● Book interpreter support for presentations ● Field trip to local library ● Field trip to community or recreation centres

Figure 4: Sample Unit Plan – Accessing Community Services

Frontloading. The goal of this unit is for learners to have the knowledge, skills and confidence needed to access community services for themselves and their families. The instructor will begin by talking about community places, using

colour images to elicit responses. The images can support classroom discussion with questions such as:

- Where do you live?
- What is your address?
- Is there a school near your home? A park?
- Do you go to the recreation centre?
- Where is your bank?

This activity permits the instructor to ascertain the learners' background knowledge and language skills in order to determine the needs of the group.

Oral vocabulary can be developed in a variety of ways, such as group games and question and answer activities. For example, learners can use images of various community locations as a prompt to ask and answer the question "Where are you going?" while moving around the classroom. Picture and word flashcards can be used for matching activities, phonics development and writing activities. Developing the concept of where learners are in the world should also be incorporated at this stage in the learning. Using flashcards for activities such as recognizing one's own address, matching common form words such as Address and City with the learner's address and city, and oral repetition of personal information all set the stage for future learning.

The ability to recognize and follow simple directions such as "Go straight" or "Turn right" is also necessary for learners to successfully navigate their communities. Daily practice of direction words using movement is a fun way to prepare learners for map reading and following directions.

Related Skills. When learners have basic competency with community vocabulary, their own personal information and simple direction words, they are ready for instruction in related skills. Map reading, which may be a very challenging task for foundational learners, can be scaffolded by beginning with 3-dimensional maps that can be manipulated. A simple 3-dimensional map can be created with streets drawn on flip chart paper and box "buildings" labelled with image flashcards of community places. Learners can be asked to move from one location to another by following oral directions, to describe the location of the places on the map, and to provide the address of map locations. Simple teacher-created maps, map apps, and authentic maps can be introduced as learners' competency increases. Apps such as Google Maps can provide practice in following directions, as can more low-tech activities such as having one learner read directions to another as they move about the classroom. Using a simple paper or online map to guide a walk around the neighbourhood provides an opportunity to follow directions and to practice asking for help. By practicing in a safe, supported setting, learners will build learner confidence to use this language in real-life situations.

Forms are ubiquitous in highly literate societies and thus literacy learners require this skill in order to access community services. Build upon learners' oral knowledge of their personal information, beginning with very simple and working up to more complex forms. Explicit teaching of how to use one's

identification to fill in the required information on forms is essential to developing this skill.

Identifying Resources. Presentations from immigrant and refugee serving agencies, community organizations such as public libraries and emergency services can help learners to understand what supports, activities and help is available to them. Again, first-language support whenever possible increases learner comprehension and provides them an opportunity to ask questions in their own language. Meeting someone from an agency or a library creates a sense of connection for learners and increased the likelihood that they will access these resources for themselves and their families. If subsidized programs are available in your community, assisting learners to apply for transit and recreation subsidies supports learner integration by reducing the financial burden of traveling to class as well as enabling them to access recreational activities that contribute to learner wellness.

Community Connections. A field trip to a local recreation centre presents many learning opportunities. Before the trip, learners can use maps to plan how to arrive at the destination, read the activity schedule for the centre and practice asking for assistance. If the recreation programs offer financial subsidies for low income clients, forms can be downloaded and filled in with assistance in the classroom. On location, learners can drop off their application forms, take a tour of the facility and even participate in fitness classes or gym activities. By visiting the centre in person, learners are much more likely to feel comfortable accessing the programs, classes and activities themselves or for their families. Again, following the field trip, many group and individual learning tasks can be completed, including writing the directions for travel to and from the centre, creating a future exercise schedule and talking about what learners enjoyed most in their experience.

CONCLUSION

This paper has discussed ways in which the transformative nature of the REFLECT model has been retained in a community-based and settlement focused ELL literacy program. The program described provides explicit L2 and literacy skills instruction, while attending to learners' settlement concerns. As Chapman & Williams (2015) highlight, learning can be transformative, even when programs and funders require specific outcomes or themes, by ensuring that L2 and literacy learning connects to improved circumstances for learners. In our context, this means learners both develop skills and the cultural capital needed to access available if they so choose.

Programs and classroom teachers can reduce barriers to social services by listening to learners' lived experiences and responding with instruction that addresses learners' concerns both in and out of the classroom. Teachers can work alongside learners in their goals to improve their circumstances by working with learners to develop skills and knowledge that will increase their ability to access services. By identifying available resources in the local community and by forging connections with social service providers, programs can support learners

who wish to access services to take the first step in accessing those services. Transformative learning experiences support access to social services and contribute to greater learner independence in the long term.

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